

Greener Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology Research

ISSN: 2276-7835 ICV 2012: 5.62

Stiffened Sandwich Beam Using Glass Fiber Reinforced Inorganic Phosphate Cement (IPC)

By

Mazen Alshaaer

Research Article

Stiffened Sandwich Beam Using Glass Fiber Reinforced Inorganic Phosphate Cement (IPC)

Mazen Alshaaer

Deanship of Academic Research, The University of Jordan, Amman 11942, Jordan. Department of Physics, College of Science and Humanitarian Studies, Salman Bin Abdul Aziz University, Alkharj, Saudi Arabia.

Email: mazen72@yahoo.com, Tel: 00962-776330873, Fax: +962-6-5300815

ABSTRACT

This paper deals with ordinary and stiffened sandwich beam using fiber reinforced Inorganic Phosphate Cement (IPC) with a polyurethane foam core. Novel IPC stiffeners are proposed and their performance to achieve composite stiffness of sandwich structures is investigated. Experimental and analytical methods are presented assuming that the specific response of beams in bending can be assimilated to elastic behaviour. This analysis method based on analysing a sandwich beam would be to treat it as I-beam. Three different structures of Sandwich beams with Inorganic Phosphate Cement (IPC) matrix composite faces and stiffeners were prepared for the experimental work; an ordinary sandwich structure (OSB), reinforced core sandwich (RCS), and integral blade sandwich (IBS). A good correlation was found with the theoretical analysis. The results confirm that the IPC-stiffeners improve the deflection resistance, and strength of the structures. In this study, the overall stiffness of the 85 cm span sandwich beams increased by factor of 7.6. Although the IBS structure expressed similar deflection behavior to RCS verse applied load, the experimental results show that this structure loses its integrity under lower applied load compared with RCS.

Keywords: Inorganic calcium phosphate cement, sandwich structure, deflection.

1. INTRODUCTION

For many years, light core sandwich construction has been considered as an alternative to many conventional structures. A sandwich structure is defined a special form of a laminated composite comprising of a combination of different materials that are bonded to each other so as to utilize the properties of each separate component to the structural advantage of the whole assembly (Awad et al., 2012; Zhenkun et al., 2012; Chen et al., 2011; Awad et al., 2010). Development of lightweight core and faces materials has continued from the 1940s to today in an effort to reduce the weight of sandwich beams and to increase its strength and stiffness. Fibre composite sandwich structures are being increasingly used in applications requiring high bending stiffness and strength, combined with low weight. Sandwich structures generally consist of face sheets (skins) made of fibres which sandwiches the lightweight core material in the middle. In a sandwich structures, the strong and stiff skins carry most of the in-plane and bending loads while the core mainly bears the transverse shear and normal load. These structures are attractive structural materials for use in aerospace, maritime, and civil structures because of their high performance (e.g. bending stiffness). In this research, the core of the sandwich beams is made from polyurethane, and faces are made from a new room temperature hardening phosphate cement whose setting time can be extended, has been developed at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB). This material is called Inorganic Phosphate Cement (IPC) and is available under the commercial brand name Vubonite (Mosselmans et al., 2007; Alshaaer et al., 2011). Due to its non-alkaline environment during and after setting and hardening, IPC can be combined with glass fibre reinforcement. Such a textile reinforced cementitious composite is an interesting material in those applications where high load-bearing capacity, good fire resistance and lightweight constructions are demanded (Cuypers, 2002). IPC is a two-component system, consisting of a calcium silicate powder and a phosphoric acid based solution of metal oxides (Alshaaer et al., 2011). After hardening, the material's properties are similar to those of cement-based materials. IPC represents a novel new class of room-temperature-setting chemically bonded materials with remarkable thermal, structural and rheological properties that are ideal for matrixes of fibre reinforced composite materials (Won et al., 2013; Zenkert et al., 2004; Cuypers, 2002; Vinson, 2001; Zenkert, 1995). The first purpose of the present article paper is to perform an experimental and theoretical study on the IPC composite-based sandwich beams. The other purpose is to make some studies that explore how well using of IPC-stiffeners, as new material, through the weak core between the two

IPC-faces might complete purely the basis of the minimum structural weight needed to carry specific loads with high stiffness. The relation between the applied load and the deflection of the material (stiffness) is the only design constraint imposed in the present studies, and the approach used classical concepts of both sandwich beams, and I-beams. Sandwich beams having rectangular - cross-sections are compared with similar IPC-stiffeners reinforced sandwich beams (Won et al., 2013; Gara et al., 2012; Vinson, 2001).

2. NOVEL LIGHT- WEIGHT IPC-STIFFENERS FOR SANDWICH STRUCTURES

In sandwich structures, stiffeners are required to provide effective bond between the face plates and the light core. The stiffeners should be designed to satisfy three basic requirements (Sun et al., 2012): (1) providing interface slipping resistance, (2) preventing complete 'pull-out' from the core, and (3) enhancing the cross section shear resistance to resist vertical load. The proposed stiffeners are made from IPC-glass fibre composite as shown in Fig. 1. The inserted IPC-stiffeners (used in "I" beam) link the two face IPC plates preventing them from tensile separation and to provide bond enhancement between the polyurethane core and face plates. These stiffeners have ability to withstand extreme loads without loss of structural integrity. The effects of these stiffeners on the central deflection as a function of applied load of the sandwich beams are evaluated and compared with ordinary sandwich beams.

3. METHODS AND MATERIALS

3.1 IPC matrix composite faces and stiffeners

The faces and stiffeners of the sandwich beams were prepared by using Fiber Reinforced Inorganic Phosphate Cement (IPC). IPC is a two-component system, consisting of a calcium silicate powder and a phosphate acid-based solution of metal oxides (Alshaaer et al., 2011). The powder component, Wollastonite (CaSiO₃) NYAD@200 of NYCO was used. The liquid mixture is a phosphoric acid solution, containing metal cations and a retarding agent following (Mosselmans et al., 2007). The weight ratio of powder to liquid used for all IPC mixtures in this research was 1/1.25, corresponding to a Ca/P ratio of 1.23. The two components of the IPC, the liquid and the powder, were mixed for five minutes at a speed of 1500 rpm with a blade mixer, in order to obtain a homogeneous mixture. Laminates in this work were fabricated by hand lay-up technique (Cuypers, 2002). The amount of matrix used per layer was 1600 g/m². Chopped glass fibre mats (2D-random) with a fibre density of 300 g/m² were used as reinforcement. The fibre diameter was 14 µm for all fibres. The length of the chopped fibres was 50 mm. The E-glass fibre reinforcement consists of fibre bundles rather than single fibres. The number of fibers per bundle was ± 1500 for 2D-random reinforcement.

3.2 Design of sandwich beams

Three different structures of Sandwich beams with Inorganic Phosphate Cement (IPC) matrix composite faces and stiffeners were prepared for the experimental work. The first structure, Figure (1)A, was a typical sandwich structure (OSB) from two IPC-faces separated by weak core, which was made from polyurethane (Gara et al., 2012; Sun et al., 2012; Cuypers, 2002). The second structure is reinforced core sandwich (RCS), Figure (1)B. This structure was composed from two IPC composite faces, and connected by two IPC-stiffeners to increase the overall stiffness of the beam and polyurethane core (Sohel et al., 2012). In the second structure, each IPC-stiffener is composed from one-layer E-glass fibre 2D-random reinforced IPC laminates. The third structure, Figure (1)C, is integral blade sandwich (IBS). This structure composed from two faces separated by two IPC-stiffeners without light core. From each structure, three beams were prepared. All these sandwich beams are post cured at 60 °C for 24 hours after leaving them 24 hours under room temperature.

Figure (1): Design of IPC compoiste-based sandwich beams; A) Ordinary sandwich beam (OSB), and B) Reinforced core sandwich (RCS), C) Integral blade sandwich (IBC).

Table 1: Dimensions and properties of the sandwich beams

Length , (L), (mm)	850
Length between the upper supports (L_1), (mm) – Four point bending test	150
Length between the lower supports (L_2), (mm)– Four point bending test	750
Width of beam (b), (mm)	200
Distance between centroids of the sandwich (d), (mm)	82.40
Thickness of the core (t_c), (mm)	80
Thickness of the face (t_f), (mm)	2.40
Thickness of the beam (t), mm	84.8
Young modulus of elasticity of the IPC - glass fiber (E_f), (MPa)	16000
Shear modulus of the core (G_c), (MPa)	2.5
Total thickness of the IPC-stiffeners (t_b) of RCS and IBS, (mm)	2.4
Separation between the IPC-stiffeners (t_s) of RCS and IBS, (mm)	80
Layers number of the IPC - glass fibers face	2
Layers number of the IPC - glass fibers stiffener	1
Poisons ratio of IPC (ν_{IPC})	0.3
L/b	4.3

Stiffness of these sandwich beams is a function of several parameters, particularly length (L), thickness of the core (t_c) and number of layers of the fibre reinforced IPC faces (k). Three series of OSB, RCS, and IBS were prepared. The dimensions and properties of sandwich beams used in the experimental study are presented in Table 1.

3.3 Four-point bending test

The sandwich beams are tested in four-point bending. Testing is performed at room temperature with an Instron universal testing machine model 4505 (MEMC-Vrije Universiteit Brussel). The beam's dimensions are: height (d), width (b), the distance between the upper supports (L_1) mm, the applied load (P) and the distance between the lower supports (L_2) as shown in Table 1. The four-point bending test set up is shown in Figure 2. This experimental work was carried out to investigate the performance of ordinary IPC- based sandwich beams (OSB), reinforced core sandwich (RCS), and integral blade sandwich (IBS). Three beams with each structure were tested. Concentrated load was applied at the mid-span of supported beams. The load was applied in displacement- controlled mode with a speed of 0.2 mm/min. The resultant central deflection was measured and recorded.

Figure (2): The four-point bend test of IPC-sandwich beams.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Basic deflection behavior of the ordinary sandwich beams (OSB) versus applied load

In these experiments, the sandwich beams have the thickness t_f and elastic modulus E_f . The core has thickness t_c and modulus E_c . The flexural rigidity is then (Zenkert et al., 2004):

$$D = \int E_z^2 dz = \frac{E_f t_f^3}{6} + \frac{E_f t_f d^2}{2} + \frac{E_c t_c^3}{12} = 2D_f + D_o + D_c \tag{1}$$

For these IPC-based sandwich constructions, the core/face thickness ratio is 17 and the face/core modulus ratio is 6400 (see table 1). The faces are thin compared with the core, i.e., $t_f \ll t_c$, also the polyurethane core has a much lower modulus than that of the face, i.e., $E_c \ll E_f$. Thus for these sandwich beams, the flexural rigidity can be written approximately as:

$$D = \frac{E_f t_f d^2}{2} \tag{2}$$

When the sandwich beam is subjected to shear forces it will deform without volume change (Cuypers, 2002). This deformation can be divided into two parts, transverse and shear deformation (Zenkert, 1995). The transverse deformation of an element equal γ_{dx} and in order to find all the deformation an integration is performed over the length of the beam. For the homogeneous cross-section the shear stiffness, S , is often written as

$$S = \frac{Gh}{k} \tag{3}$$

Where G is shear modulus, h the height and k a shear factor.

The shear stiffness, S , is found by calculating the average shear angle of the cross section. Using the approximations for a sandwich with thin faces, $t_f \ll t_c$, weak core, $E_c \ll E_f$ and that shear modulus of the faces G_f are large, the shear stiffness, S , can be written as

$$S = \frac{G_c d^2}{t_c} \tag{4}$$

As result of four- point bending test (FPBT), deformation of the beams occurs as a function of both shear deformation $w_s(x)$ and bending deformation $w_b(x)$, equation (5).

$$w(x) = w_b(x) + w_s(x) = f(D, Geometry) + f(S, Geometry) \tag{5}$$

In the region between the inner and outer supporter, L_2-L_1 , the transverse force is constant and equal to P , which in turns means that the shear stress in the core is constant over a fairly long part of the beam. Between the inner supports, over a length of L_1 , the bending moment is constant and equal to $P(L_2-L_1)/2$, while in the same zone the transverse force is identically equal to zero. The deformation and the maximum deflection of the beam can easily be found by ordinary sandwich theorem (Zenkert et al., 2004).

$$w\left(\frac{L_2 - L_1}{2}\right) = \frac{P(L_2 - L_1)^2(L_2 + 2L_1)}{24D} + \frac{PL_2}{2S} \tag{6}$$

Figure (3): The theoretical and experimental elastic deflection of the sandwich beams as a function of applied load.

The maximum deflection, in the middle of the beam can similarly be written

$$w\left(\frac{L_2}{2}\right) = \frac{P(L_2 - L_1)(2L_2^2 + 2L_1L_2 - L_1^2)}{24D} + \frac{PL_2}{2S} \tag{7}$$

By substituting equations 2, 4 in equation 7, it becomes possible to calculate the maximum deformation of the first structure (ordinary sandwich beams) after performing FPB test. The theoretical and experimental central (maximum) deflection of the OSB verses applied load is reported in Fig. 3A. It was observed that the experimental curves are in good agreement with curves resulting from theoretical calculations as shown in equation (7). The ultimate load was 3487 N with a corresponding deflection of 12 mm. These results show that the theoretical equations fit with the IPC-based sandwich beams as new material.

4.2 Reinforced core sandwich (RCS) with IPC-stiffeners

Analysing a sandwich structure with reinforced core would be to treat it as I-beam and is done by considering a sandwich of width b and an I-beam with flanges of width b , (Figure 4).

Figure (4): The equivalent web width of an I-beam.

By finding the thickness of the web b_e , in the I-beam so that the two cross sections will have the same flexural rigidity. The equivalent b_e can be found from this relation (Zenkert et al., 2004).

$$\frac{E_c b t_c^3}{12} = \frac{E_f b_e t_c^3}{12} \Rightarrow b_e = \frac{E_c}{E_f} b \tag{8}$$

According to the RCS structure, the total shear stiffness of the beam resulted from the two IPC-stiffeners and the core. We can consider that the two IPC-stiffeners are stretched to the width b , then its new stiffness parameters can be calculated as shown in Figure (5).

Figure (5): The equivalent sandwich core of IPC-stiffeners and Polyurethane core

$$\frac{G_{eq.} d^2 b_e}{t_c} = \frac{G_{IPC} d^2 b}{t_c} \Rightarrow G_{eq.} = \frac{G_{IPC} b_e}{b} \quad (9)$$

$$S_{eq.} = \sum S_i = S_{IPC} = \frac{G_{eq.} d^2}{t_c} + \frac{G_c d^2}{t_c} \quad (10)$$

The applied load versus central deflection curves of RCS structure are shown in Fig 5B. The experimental results fit well with the theoretical calculations, according to equations 7 and 10, of the beams with IPC stiffeners. Compared with OSB, the IPC-stiffeners increased the overall stiffness of the sandwich structure by factor of 7.6. Also the failure load increased by factor 2, which is 6821 N for RCS. However the effect of the IPC-stiffeners is decreased with increasing length of the IPC sandwich beams. This can be shown by equation (7).

4.3 Integral blade sandwich (IBS)

The central deflection of Integral blade sandwich (IBS) versus the applied load is reported in Fig. 3C. There is a good agreement between the theoretical calculations and the experimental curves of this structure. Due to the fact that $E_c \ll E_f$, the removal of polyurethane core had a negligible effect on the deflection behavior of this structure compared with RCS structure as shown in Fig. 3B. Therefore, these two structures, RCS and IBS, expressed the same stiffness behavior under applied load. The failure load of IBS is 4232 N which is less than that of RCS; 6821 N. Accordingly, the polyurethane core improves the overall stability of the structure under applied load and increases the failure load by 60%.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The numerical results reveal that IPC-stiffeners have a significant effect on the bending behaviors of sandwich beams. This experimental work accompanied with corresponding theoretical analysis confirms that the sandwich structures with fibre reinforcement IPC faces, as new material, and stiffeners fit well with the general sandwich structures equations. A good agreement is observed between the theoretical calculations and the experimental measurements of IPC sandwich beams with different structure: ORB, RCS, and IBS. Observable improvements in the deflection resistance and overall stiffness of the structures are observed with IPC-stiffeners, RCS. In this study, the overall stiffness of the 85 cm span sandwich beams increased by factor of 7.6. Although the IBS structure expressed similar deflection behavior to RCS verse applied load, the experimental results show that this structure loses its integrity under lower applied load compared with RCS.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Dr. Mazen Alshaaer wishes to acknowledge the support of the Department of Mechanics of Materials and Constructions (MEMC), Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB), for providing the laboratory facilities. Thanks are also extended to Dr Heidi Cuypers and Prof. Jan Wastiels for their help.

6. REFERENCES

- Alshaaer M, Cuypers H, Mosselmans G, Rahier H, Wastiels J. "Evaluation of a low temperature hardening Inorganic Phosphate Cement for high-temperature applications", *Cement and Concrete Research*, 2011, 41, 38-45
- Alshaaer M, Cuypers H, Rahier H, Wastiels J. Production of monetite-based Inorganic Phosphate Cement (M-IPC) using hydrothermal post curing (HTPC), *Cement and Concrete Research*, 2011, 41, 30–37
- Awad ZK, Aravinthan T, Zhuge Y, Gonzalez F. A review of engineering applications, *Materials and Design*, 2012, 33, 534–544
- Awad ZK, Aravinthan T, Zhuge Y. Cost optimum design of structural fibre composite sandwich panel for flooring applications. In: *CICE 2010 – the 5th international conference on FRP composites in civil engineering*, Beijing, China; 2010.

- Chen JS, Sharma B, Sun CT. Dynamic behaviour of sandwich structure containing spring-mass resonators, *Composite Structures*, 2011, 93, 2120–2125
- Cuyppers H. Analysis and design of sandwich panels with brittle matrix composite faces for building applications, PhD thesis, Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB), Belgium 2002
- Gara F, Ragni L, Roia D, Dezi L. Experimental tests and numerical modelling of wall sandwich panels, *Engineering Structures*, 2012, 37, 193–204
- Mosselmans G, Biesemans M, Willem R, Wastiels J, Leermakers M, Rahier H, Brughmans S, Van Mele B. Thermal hardening and structure of a phosphorus containing cementitious model material phosphoric acid–wollastonite, *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, 2007, 88, 3, 723–729
- Sohel K M A, Richard Liew J Y, Yan J B, Zhang M H, Chia K S. Behavior of Steel–Concrete–Steel sandwich structures with lightweight cement composite and novel shear connectors, *Composite Structures*, 2012, 94, 3500–3509
- Sun Z, Jeyaraman J, Sun S, Hua X, Chen H. Carbon-fiber aluminum-foam sandwich with short aramid-fiber interfacial toughening, *Composites: Part A*, 2012, 43, 2059–2064
- Vinson J R. Sandwich structures. *Appl Mech Rev*, 2001, 54, 201–14
- Won S G, Bae S H, Cho J R, Bae S R, Jeong W B. Three-layered damped beam element for forced vibration analysis of symmetric and wick structures with a viscoelastic core, *Finite Elements in Analysis and Design*, 2013, 68, 39–51
- Zenkert D, Shipsha A, Persson K. Static indentation and unloading response of sandwich beams. *Composites: Part B*, 2004, 35, 511–22
- Zenkert D. *An Introduction to Sandwich Construction*, EMAS, 1995.
- Zhenkun L, Wei Q, Libo D. Flexural effects of sandwich beam with a plate insert under in-plane bending, *Optics & Laser Technology*, 2012, 44, 1223–1231